

**WEB FRONT-END AND BACK-END TECHNOLOGIES IN
PROGRAMMING**

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Sign in .

Web programming dynamic and interactive websites work exit own into takes both front-end and back-end technologies according to requires experience . _ Front-end technologies user interface design and user to the experience attention focuses on backend technologies and the server side logic , data bases and applications functions manages _ This article modern web development on the way out their importance clarity by entering this technologies about complete information will give .

HTML (hypertext designation language):

HTML web content make up for basis being service does _ It's web pages skeleton structure provides headings , paragraphs , images _ and links such as elements determines _ HTML language Understanding front-end development exits for good organize done and semantic in terms of meaningful web documents Create for very important _

CSS (Cascading Style Sheets):

CSS style and presentation for is necessary . It works to the exits of the website layout , colors , fonts and another visual aspects manage enable will give . HTML and CSS _ separate to the design modular and supported the approach provides , general user experience increases .

JavaScript:

JavaScript to web pages interactivity and dynamic action adds _ A lot edged script language as it works to the exits sensitive and interesting user interfaces to create possibility will give . JavaScript client on the side it is done while the page again in real time without requiring download updates done increase enable will give .

Back-end technologies :

Node.js:

JavaScript engine built in Node.js on the server side using JavaScript to work makes it easier . His to events based , non-blocking architecture him

expandable and high fruitful applications for very suitable does _ Node.js is especially real-time applications and API creation for famous _ Django and Flask:

Django and Flask to Python based on frames is , each of them web development on the way out different different needs satisfies . Django, top level framework , authentication , ORM and others for installed components with complete stacked the solution present is enough Flask, another from the side , work to the exits project requirements based on components in choosing more flexibility which provides light frame is considered

Laravel:

Laravel to PHP based on frame being his own elegant syntax and work exits for comfortable features with famous _ It is in the configuration attention focuses on this while projects start and to keep makes it easier . Laravel itself into Eloquent ORM, Blade template mechanism and strong ecosystem such as features own into takes and this his popularity contribution adds _

Between Front-end and Back-end mutually effect :

Efficient web programming front-end and backend technologies in the middle continuously requires cooperation . _ Front-end components user interface and server logic in the middle data and actions exchange with a back-end through a provider API is connected . This integration united and sensitive user experience provides .

Summary :

Summary by doing in other words , modern , sensitive and feature- rich web applications to create the goal did web development exits for front-end and back-end technologies comprehensively to understand very important _ Between HTML, CSS and JavaScript in the front- end synergy , back side the power of Node.js, Django, Flask or Laravel with together modern of web programming basis organize does _ Technology in development continue enough since , this from changes informed to be web development release of innovations previous in the ranks to stay for very important

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